

D2.1: Mapping of the ethical Issues in XR-overview of Ethical Frameworks: A Scoping Review

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<p>ABSTRACT:</p>	<p>The use of immersive technologies such as virtual, augmented, mixed reality and the Metaverse raises many issues of ethical concern. The various ethical issues, if left unaddressed, may impact human well-being over time. Immersive technologies are used in entertainment, commerce, education, health and the military. Subsequently, there is a broad spectrum of users with various degrees of competencies and vulnerabilities. Special attention would be regarding the long-term effect of immersive technologies on children and the lack of consideration of inclusivity for all persons in society. Several publications have highlighted ethical issues related to immersive technologies, and some have sought to address these issues by proposing solutions or approaches in the form of frameworks, codes of conduct or best practices.</p> <p>This review examined grey and white literature between 2000-2023 to identify the various proposed or adopted ethical frameworks, codes of conduct or best practices for immersive technologies. The research method was qualitative and adopted Arksey and O'Malley's scoping review methodological approach.</p> <p>A total of 28 papers were selected for in-depth analysis. Approximately 70% of the selected papers were published between 2020 and 2022. Using an inductive thematic analysis method, six fundamental values and twenty-two corresponding principles were generated. The main values are respect for persons, well-being, safety, integrity and trust, justice, and responsiveness. The dominant principles noted in the papers are privacy, informed consent, responsibility, transparency, and freedom. The issuers of the papers were predominantly academicians. The normative approaches to addressing ethical issues are organised into four domains: society and governance, industry, research/academic organisations, and individuals. General recommendations are as follows: 1) the application of existing laws or guidelines to address legal issues with immersive technologies, 2) industry practitioners should adopt inclusive approaches to design and development, 3) researchers should minimise potential harm for participants, and 4) individuals, i.e., users of immersive technologies should be empowered and sincere in their use of a virtual space concerning identity and conduct.</p>
<p>Keyword List:</p>	<p>Virtual reality, augmented reality, mixed reality, ethics, extended reality, immersive technologies</p>

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1 Mapping of the ethical Issues in XR-overview of ethical frameworks: A Scoping Review

1.1 Background

Extended reality (XR) technologies are double-edged swords. Their usefulness and potential are undeniable: not only are they quickly moving towards ubiquity; their fields of application are virtually endless. At the same time, for these technologies to function, users and their environments may be exposed to new risks and other ethical/philosophical issues that may have negative and/or unintended effect and/or consequences. As the technology is developing and becoming more common, Europe must strive to establish an ethical governance framework for XR technologies that preserve European values and virtues while guiding not only users but also, most significantly, designers and developers of the technology (Fox & Thornton, 2022; Stephens, 2022). This is a major aim of the XR4Human project.

This deliverable is the first of the four WP2 deliverables, collectively meant to "map, examine, and provide a conceptual and normative framework on the ethical issues – including the issues of inclusivity – arising in XR technologies". D2.1 will provide an overview and preliminary assessment of relevant ethical frameworks, codes of conduct, and good practices in XR development and use. The scoping task of D2.1 is a necessary step meant to serve the purposes of other WPs, such as but not limited to WP2 and WP5. For WP2, D2.1 provides inputs for D2.2 (overview of possible forms of XR risks and harms), D2.3 (models of harm that could arise in XR technologies; and D2.4 (ethical issues beyond risks and harm). For WP5, D2.1 provides the benchmark or at least an overview of what is already addressed and on which the XR4Human Code of Conduct (D5.2) can use as its starting point and possibly as the foundation.

1.2 Research Question

What are the relevant ethical frameworks, codes of conduct and good practices related to XR?

1.3 Specific Aim and Objectives

Aim: To provide an overview of relevant ethical frameworks, codes of conduct and good practices related to extended reality

Specific Objectives:

- To assess foundational ethical principles in the noted guidelines.
- To identify ethical issues addressed and the means proposed to address the identified issues and note the commonalities and/or differences in the various approaches.
- To identify gaps in ethical issues addressed in the noted guidelines.

2 Methods

This paper adopted the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for systematic reviews and meta-analysis) scoping review research methodology. The overarching goal of a scoping review is mapping relevant literature on a research subject/area (Moher et al., 2009). The scoping review method was developed by Arksey and O'Malley in 2005 and employs a framework with the following steps: 1) identifying the research question, 2) identifying relevant studies and study selection, 4) charting the data, and 5) collating, summarising, and reporting the results, and 6) a consultation (optional) (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Moher et al., 2009). A preliminary literature search reveals no other study mapping the ethics guidelines for immersive technologies. However, Jobin et al. performed a global landscape of ethics guidelines for

Artificial intelligence (Jobin et al., 2019). Jobin et al. developed a protocol based on the PRISMA framework they note as pilot-tested and calibrated. Given the similarity of the research question, we adopted the protocol outlined by Jobin et al. for this scoping review within the context of ethics guidelines for immersive technologies. We note however, that Jobin et al.'s focus was on grey literature; therefore, we expanded our search to include both grey and academic literature (Jobin et al., 2019).

2.1 Data Sources and search strategy

The research team for this scoping review was multi-disciplinary, comprising academicians and practitioners with expertise in ethics, philosophy, neuroscience, and industry practitioners working with immersive technology. In January, the research team developed and agreed on the search terms in accordance with a priori knowledge and experience with immersive technologies. The databases-Scopus and IEEE were identified as suitable for a comprehensive search (see table 1.0 below). The approved search terms were submitted to the medical librarian at the University of Oslo, Faculty of Medicine, who completed the database search on February 8, 2023. The date limit was 2000–2023.

Database	Search terms	Number of retrieved abstracts	
Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (ethic* OR bioethic* OR philosoph* OR integrity OR moral* OR "human centred" OR "human centered") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (framework* OR guideline* OR guidance* OR regulation* OR regulatory OR law OR laws OR legislat* OR legal OR norm OR norms OR normative OR "code of conduct" OR (good W/2 practice*)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((interactive W/2 (media* OR experience*)) OR metaverse OR xr OR xr4* OR (immersive W/2 (technolog* OR environment*)) OR (virtual W/2 (realit* OR environment*)) OR ((virtualis* OR virtualiz*) W/2 (technolog* OR network*)) OR (augmented W/2 realit*) OR (mixed W/2 realit*) OR (extended W/2 realit*)))	1236	
IEEE	(((interactive NEAR/2 (media OR experience*)) OR metaverse OR xr OR xr4* OR (immersive NEAR/2 (technology OR technologies)) OR (immersive NEAR/2 (environment OR environments)) OR (virtual NEAR/2 (reality OR realities OR environment*)) OR (virtuali* NEAR/2 (technolog* OR network*)) OR (augmented NEAR/2 (reality OR realities)) OR (mixed NEAR/2 (reality OR realities)) OR (extended NEAR/2 (reality OR realities))) AND (framework OR frameworks OR guideline OR guidelines OR guidance OR guidances OR regulation OR regulations OR regulatory OR law OR laws OR legislation OR legislations OR legislative OR legal OR norm OR norms OR normative OR "code of conduct" OR (good NEAR/2 practice*)) AND (ethic OR ethical OR ethics OR ethically OR bioethic OR bioethical OR philosophi* OR integrity OR integrities OR moral OR morals OR morality OR moralities OR "human centred" OR "human centered"))	352	
Summary		Total number of records	1588
		After deduplication	1359

Table 1.0 Search terms used by the librarian and number of abstracts retrieved for analysis.

Following the methodology of Jobin, Ienca and Vayena (2019), two researchers (SC and JA) each performed a Google search while logged out of personal accounts, in private browsing mode and with web history, cache, and cookies deleted (Jobin et al., 2019). Every link in the first 100th results was followed and screened for frameworks or guidelines, which identified further documents for inclusion. The search identified academic peer-reviewed articles and grey literature from academic, governmental, or non-governmental organisations and conferences. One important search finding was a news article highlighting the South Korean Government's publication of Ethics guidelines for the Metaverse (Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022). SC conducted an exhaustive citation chaining for selected full-text documents,

but only three met the inclusion criteria. The screening and full-text reading were conducted between February 10 – March 17, 2023. Although approximately 22 documents were identified during citation chaining, only three were included. Since a recently published document was identified as relevant based on the eligibility criteria, it was manually inputted as it was published after the initial database search.

2.2 Title and abstract relevance screening

The citations were uploaded into the web-based platform Rayyan for screening and selection of abstracts based on eligibility criteria outlined in Table 2.0. Initial screening was done by SC, and a secondary screening by ES. RdcB was assigned as a reviewer to decide on unresolved conflicts. Documents were excluded if there was no reference to any of the various forms of immersive technologies, i.e., virtual reality, augmented reality, mixed reality, or the Metaverse. Further exclusion was based on whether the documents did not discuss nor utilise a normative approach to ethical issues with immersive technologies or if the authors discussed immersive technologies without reference to ethics. Additionally, documents where full texts could not be retrieved were excluded.

Screening	
Sources considered	<p>Types: Abstract and citation databases of scholarly (academia) literature, guidelines, recommendations, policy documents, regulations, Framework, official standards,</p> <p>Issuers: academicians, institutions, Government and affiliated agencies, Non-governmental Organisations, professional societies, non-profit organisations</p> <p>Language: English Only</p>
Sources excluded	Conference summaries, papers reporting the results of interventional studies using immersive technologies, videos, images, podcasts, blog articles, journalistic articles, syllabi, books
Eligibility	
Sources included	<p>Explicitly refer to "immersive technologies" or extended reality or virtual reality or mixed reality, or augmented reality, or the Metaverse</p> <p>Self-proclaim to be a guideline, code of ethics, code of conduct, best practice, or ethics framework for virtual reality, mixed reality, augmented reality or Metaverse</p> <p>Expressed in normative or prescriptive language (modal verbs or imperatives)</p> <p>Generally guiding (i.e., covers all or several fields/applications)</p>
Sources excluded	<p>Does not mention immersive technologies, extended reality, virtual reality, or the Metaverse.</p> <p>Does not identify itself as an ethics guideline, code, code of conduct, best practice, or framework</p> <p>Not expressed in normative or prescriptive language</p> <p>Narrowly field-specific</p>

Table 2.0 Eligibility criteria—The organisation of this table is adapted from: Jobin, A., Ienca, M. & Vayena, E. The global landscape of AI ethics guidelines. *Nat Mach Intell* 1, 389–399 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0088-2> then adjusted based on the search criteria related to ethics guidelines for immersive technologies

2.3 Data synthesis and coding strategy

Twenty-eight full-text documents were identified for coding and data analysis. Documents were included if the authors self-identified in the title that they were proposing a code of ethics, a guideline or guidance, best practice, or a framework for any or all immersive technologies. All documents were in English based on the search criteria. After the initial title and abstract screening, we excluded 1344 that did not meet our eligibility criteria. The final number of documents selected from abstract and title screening was 15. We identified an additional 30 documents search, citation chaining and manual input. These total full text for screening was 45; 17 texts were excluded for not meeting the eligibility criteria. Subsequently, 28 documents were uploaded to NVIVO version 1.7.1. for coding. The files were copied and shared among five researchers (SC, ES, AK, JA, and RdcB) who individually coded based on the pre-

determined categories: 1) Ethical Issues, 2) Foundational Ethical Principles and 3) Approaches. Although the main thematic categories were pre-determined, the coding of the texts was entirely inductive. The researchers met weekly to discuss the identified codes and explanations given for each. Codes similar in meaning or context were merged. However, a consensus was not sought for the inclusion of dissimilar codes. The reason was to ensure that the findings were reflective of the variations of focus in relation to the author, target audience or topic of discussion. Figure 1.0 below is a schematic representation of the retrieval and screening process. Table 3.0 outlines the 28 documents, the type of immersive technology discusses, the target audience and the geographic location of the first author or organisation.

Figure 1.0 PRISMA flow diagram explaining the retrieval and screening process. The search sources for the databases: Scopus and IEEE, Google search, citation chaining and manual input.

2.4 Data analysis and discussion

The analysis of the data, elaborated under “Results”, was accomplished by SC while the discussion section was written by SC, RdcB, and RB. SC, RdcB and RB reviewed, proofread, and revised the document. Direct quotes are used throughout the results section to support the identified themes thereby enhancing the credibility of the qualitative reporting and validation process.

3 Results

After deduplication, abstract screening and reading of full-texts, 28 documents were identified for coding and content analysis (See Table 3.0). These documents note ethical issues and suggest frameworks, guidelines, recommendations for codes of conduct and best practices for immersive technologies. Approximately 50% of the papers were written by a US-based author or organisation. Thirty-six (36%) were European issuers, the remaining from Asia and Australia.

- Sources from the USA (n=14; 50%),
- Sources from Europe (n=10; 35.7%) - Netherlands (n=4), Germany (n=2), Sweden(n=1), Finland=1, EU consortium led by Austria=1 United Kingdom=1
- Asia (n=2; 7.14%) China=1, North Korea=1
- Australia (n=2; 7.14%)

Figure 2.0 Geographic distribution of publications based on location of issuers.

Approximately 70% (n=20) of the papers were issued between 2020 and 2023, of which 17 were in 2021-2022. The main issuers were Academicians and non-profit organisations. The target audience was predominantly researchers, industry practitioners and educators. Twelve (12) of the papers were general in addressing issues related to various types of immersive technologies, while five (5) focused only on experiences with VR, four (4) focused exclusively on the Metaverse, two (2) focused on both VR and AR and one (1) addressed issues related to AR only.

Figure 3.0 Number of publications regarding ethical frameworks for immersive technologies over 20 years.

Ten issuers identified their papers as either Code (n=4), Framework (n=4), and Guidance/tools (n=1 each). Seven papers were identified as Best Practice standards or guidelines issued by Government and the professional organisation IEEE (see Figure 3.0). Eleven were categorised as others because of the variations in titles, such as approaches, considerations, and vision for the various types of immersive technologies. The target audience was practitioners in health research, particularly the impact of virtual reality in psychology and children, and industry practitioners such as developers and designers, policymakers, and educators.

Year of Publication	Title of document	Type of XR	Type of Issuers	COUNTRY OF ISSUER/AUTHORS	TARGET AUDIENCE	Retrieval
2000	New Directions: A Value-Sensitive Design Approach to Augmented Reality (Friedman & Kahn, 2000)	Augmented Reality	Academician	USA	Developers or Designers	Citation chaining
2005	Some Practical Considerations of Ethical Issues in VR Research (Behr et al., 2005)	Virtual Reality	Academician	Netherlands	Researchers	Other searches
2008	Meta-Ethics for the Metaverse: The Ethics of Virtual Worlds (Spence, 2008)	Metaverse	Academician	Australia	Designers, Administrators, Players	Scopus/IEEE
2016	Real Virtuality: A Code of Ethical Conduct. Recommendations for Good Scientific Practice and the Consumers of VR-Technology (Madary & Metzinger, 2016)	Virtual Reality	Academician	Germany	Researchers	Scopus/IEEE
2017	Asking Ethical Questions in Research using	Immersive Virtual, Augmented	Academician	Australia	Researchers	Scopus/IEEE

	Immersive Virtual and Augmented Reality Technologies with Children and Youth (Southgate et al., 2017)	and Mixed reality				
	Ethical Considerations for the Use of Virtual Reality: An Evaluation of Practices in Academia and Industry (Luro et al., 2017)	Virtual Reality	Academician	Sweden	Academic and industrial practitioners	Scopus/IEEE
2019	Ethically Aligned Design: A Vision for Prioritising Human Well-being with Autonomous and Intelligent Systems (The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, 2019)	Extended Reality	Non-profit organisation (NPO)	USA	Academic and industrial practitioners	Other searches
	Ethical Guidelines in Virtual Reality: Towards a Code of Conduct in Research (Bliznyuk, 2019)	Virtual Reality	Academician	Germany	Unspecified	Other searches
2020	Immersive Technology Standards for accessibility, inclusion, ethics, and safety (Boyd-Noronha, 2020)	Extended reality technologies	Non-profit organisation (NPO)	USA	Public-private industries, governments, and academic organisations	Other searches
	The Ethics of Realism in Virtual and Augmented Reality (Slater et al., 2020)	VR, AR	Academician	UK	Researchers, content creators, and distributors of XR systems	Citation chaining
	A Self-Guiding Tool to Conduct Research with Embodiment Technologies Responsibly (Aymerich-Franch & Fosch-Villaronga, 2020)	VR, Avatars	Academician	Netherlands	Researchers and developers	Scopus/IEEE
	The XRSI Privacy Framework (Pearlman, 2020)	XR technologies	NPO	International	Public-private industries, Governments and academic organisations.	Other search

2021	ARLEAN: An Augmented Reality Learning Analytics Ethical Framework (Christopoulos et al., 2021)	AR	Academician	Finland, Greece	Designers and educators	Scopus/IEEE
	E3XR: An Analytical Framework for Ethical, Educational and Eudaimonic XR Design (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021)	XR Technologies	Academician	USA	Designers and educators	Scopus/IEEE
	The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended reality (XR) Report: Social and multi-user spaces in VR, trolling, Harassment, and online safety (Cortese & Outlaw, 2021)	XR Technologies	Non-profit organisation (NPO)	USA	public-private industries, governments, and academic organisations	Other searches
	The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended reality (XR) Report: Who owns our second lives: Virtual clones and the right to your identity (Eriksson, 2021)	XR Technologies	Non-profit organisation (NPO)	USA	public-private industries, governments, and academic organisations	Other searches
	The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended reality (XR) Report: Ethics in Education (Magina, 2021)	XR Technologies	Non-profit organisation (NPO)	USA	public-private industries, governments, and academic organisations	Other searches
	The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended reality (XR) Report: Extended reality (XR) and the erosion of anonymity and privacy (McGill, 2021)	XR Technologies	Non-profit organisation (NPO)	USA	public-private industries, governments, and academic organisations	Other searches
	An ethical code for commercial VR/AR applications (Ramirez et al., 2021)	VR/AR	Academician	USA	Developers or designers	Citation chaining

	Toward a framework for developing virtual reality skills training in human services (Davis et al., 2021)	VR	Academician	USA	Educators and workforce administrators	
2022	The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended reality (XR) Report: Metaverse Governance (Stephens, 2022)	Metaverse	Non-profit organisation (NPO)	USA	Public-private industries, governments, and academic organisations	Other searches
	The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended reality (XR) Report: Diversity, inclusion, accessibility (Fox & Thornton, 2022)	XR Technologies	Non-profit organisation (NPO)	USA	Public-private industries, governments, and academic organisations	Other searches
	Life, the Metaverse and Everything: An Overview of Privacy, Ethics, and Governance in Metaverse (Fernandez & Hui, 2022)	Metaverse	Academician	China	Developers or designers	Scopus/IEEE
	Markkula Center: A Code of Ethics for the Metaverse (Heider, 2022)	Metaverse	Academician	USA	Unspecified	Other searches
	Responsible Design and assessment of a SARS-CoV virtual reality rehabilitation programme: guidance ethics in context (Smits et al., 2022)	Virtual Reality	Academician	Netherlands	Researchers	Scopus/IEEE
	Ethical Principles for the Metaverse (Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022)	Metaverse	Governmental agency	South Korea	Individuals and organisations in the private and public sectors, such as companies, academia, research institutes, civil society, and the Government	Other searches
	XRSI Recommendations for the Biden-	XR Technologies	NPO	International	Public-private industries,	Other search

	Harris Administration (Pearlman, 2022)				Governments and academic organisations.	
2023	XR and General Purpose AI: from values and principles to norms and standards (Laurynas Adomaitis & Grinbaum, 2023)	XR technologies	Consortium	EU consortium	Unspecified	Other search

Table 3.0 Summary of documents by type of technology, country of the issuer, and target audience

Figure 4.0 Categorisation of analysed documents

3.1 Ethical Issues

Three (3) thematic categories were noted for ethical issues, and six (6) thematic categories were coded for foundational values with 22 corresponding principles. The approaches to the identified ethical issues were organised into four domains: Society/Governance, Industry, Research Organizations, and Individuals.

The three categories for ethical Issues are related to 1) Data and use of technology, 2) Human rights concerns, and 3) Societal, Economic, and Environmental concerns.

3.1.1 Issues related to Data and use of technology

Data

The main issues related to Data were concerns regarding breach of privacy and confidentiality, the volume of data extracted, and lack of clarity in language or jargon when information is shared (Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; McGill, 2021; Pearlman, 2020; Ramirez et al., 2021; Slater et al., 2020; Southgate et al., 2017). Data breaches may be informational, volumetric or physical (Christopoulos et al., 2021; Magina, 2021; McGill, 2021; Southgate et al., 2017). Other relevant concerns are constant data capture without consent, the possibility of data being decoded and made identifiable, and data misuse. Data obfuscation makes data incomprehensible based on the technical language used and the volume of data to process (Fox & Thornton, 2022). Data obfuscation may preclude true informed consent. Data misuse may include surveillance, deception, and the possibility of covert indoctrination based on information feeds. Issues related to ensuring data privacy and consent concerning immersive technologies featured significantly across all papers.

Use of Technology

One of the main issues regarding the use of technology is the difficulty with navigating real and virtual lives/experiences (Behr et al., 2005; Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, 2019). Users of immersive technology may experience physical world re-entry problems due to issues related to virtual embodiment (Behr et al., 2005; Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Slater et al., 2020). Immersive technologies may also incorporate nudges and control the social interactions of individuals in the virtual space (Eriksson, 2021; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Ramirez et al., 2021; Slater et al., 2020; The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, 2019). Re-entry problems due to embodiment and controlled interactions may significantly impact users, but most especially vulnerable users such as children and participants in psychological research (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Slater et al., 2020; Southgate et al., 2017). The authors note several physical and psychological manifestations of re-entering physical reality from a virtual experience such as motion sickness, postural stability, cognitive and disturbances, and information overload (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Ramirez et al., 2021). One author note that re-entry problems and embodiment may manifest positively and negatively (Ramirez et al., 2021). However, it is important to emphasise that one of the main ethical concerns with re-entry and embodiment is the possible loss of agency and infringement of autonomy (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Ramirez et al., 2021; Slater et al., 2020; The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, 2019).

Certain virtual environments and especially embodiments in VR can induce changes of one's attitudes during or after the experiment (Madary & Metzinger, 2016). Changes of perception after re-entry into the physical world also affect decision making by the participant due to a false sense of or loss of agency (Madary & Metzinger, 2016). The researcher must be aware that these effects can infringe the autonomy of the participant (Bliznyuk, 2019). Cognitive, emotional and behavioural disturbances after re-entry into the physical world following the VR experience were described for VR, but they are as well valid for AR (Slater et al., 2020).

Dualism or unintended use of technologies is another ethically relevant concern.

Dual use is a well-known problem in research ethics and the ethics of technology, especially in the life sciences. Here, we use it to refer to the fact that technology can be used for something other than its intended purpose, to military applications. In the context of VR technology, one will immediately think not only of drone warfare, teleoperated weapon systems, or "virtual suicide attacks," but also of interrogation procedures and torture. It is not in the power of the scientists and engineers who develop the technology to police its use, but we can raise awareness about potential misuses of the technology as a way of contributing to precautionary steps (Madary & Metzinger, 2016, p. 10)

While the foreseeability of unintended use of technology may be a challenge, developers ought to consider the possibility and not only focus on the intended use but exercise due diligence in preventing harm.

We must consider beforehand the potential harms of virtual reality to ensure that such technologies are neither intentionally nor accidentally misused. Accounting for these new forms of harm protects both the users and developers of VR/AR, who are both fundamental to the progression of good VR and AR technology (Ramirez et al., 2021, p. 4).

3.1.2 Issues related to Human rights

The ethical issues in relation to human rights were discussed in the wider societal context and individual challenges. At the societal level, authors note concerns regarding discrimination against vulnerable and marginalised populations such as those with mental illness and children. They also note the lack of access and representativeness for persons with varying levels and types and degrees of disabilities. Others note that users of immersive technologies may experience a sense of not belonging. This was especially noted in relation to users of the Metaverse (Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022). At the individual level, immersive technologies may have negative effects on users. The main ethical challenge is in relation to harm. Harm may be physical, psychological, and/or emotional. Physical manifestations of harm include motion sickness (nausea, vomiting, disorientation, palpitations) (Behr et al., 2005; Madary & Metzinger, 2016). Psychological or emotional harm manifests as depression, confusion, trauma and aggressive behaviours such as game rage (Behr et al., 2005; Madary & Metzinger, 2016). The long-term effect of immersion is another ethically relevant issue concerning psychological harm (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Southgate et al., 2017).

Mention was also made of identity challenges and ownership of virtual space (Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Stephens, 2022). Users of immersive technologies may assume a virtual identity that is different from their physical identity. For example, the creation of virtual clones and avatars that may or may not physically or in other ways resemble or reflect the actual user. The possibility of identity theft/hacking and the right to ownership of identity and, by extension, virtual clones and avatars is a critical ethical and legal issue that needs to be addressed (Eriksson, 2021; Stephens, 2022).

Loss or compromised sense of agency was identified as an ethical issue, especially for research participants and the use of deception in virtual reality (Madary & Metzinger, 2016).

3.1.3 Issues related to Society, Economy, and the Environment

Concerns regarding the negative impact of increased application and immersive technologies on society were pervasive, especially in the papers on the Metaverse (Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Stephens, 2022). Social inclusivity and sustainability, especially regarding future generations, were discussed. There was concern about an increase in crime (real or virtual). Crime was discussed in the context of whether a crime in the real world would be considered a crime in the virtual world. For example, rape or other forms of virtual assault/violence on an avatar. On the other hand, there were concerns about actual cybercrimes such as fraud, identity theft, stalking and hacking as noted in the text excerpts below.

Crimes associated with XR are more difficult to penalise. It depends on where it occurred (XR, hybrid, or real world) and where the impact occurred (XR, hybrid, or real world) (Stephens, 2022, p. 18).

XR could be used to inflict psychological harm upon the user in the form of harassment, bullying, torture, hate speech or assault. With its strong aspects of graphic and haptic realism, embodiment and presence, it could induce trauma and exacerbate violations of personal space such as simulated touching or grabbing (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021, p. 4).

The depiction or embodiment of many kinds of immoral acts are possible in XR, including graphic acts of violence, torture, rape, robbery, and grand theft. These kinds of realistic depictions can lead to trauma, stress or anxiety (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021, p. 9).

Monetisation and lack of or insufficient governance were also concerns as it is considered an incentive to capture a wider audience (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Stephens, 2022). The monetisation of the Metaverse may inadvertently impact society's wider economy as it may "fuel global competitiveness and increase regulatory pressures as countries try to safeguard and extend their domain to XR spaces, leading to unanticipated public-private partnerships that will create new country alliances or lead to the breakdown of others"(Stephens, 2022, p. 9). Attention monetisation is addictive dependent and may lead to wasted time, money and loss of agency. (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Stephens, 2022).

XR4HUMAN – Summary of Ethical Issues

CATEGORIES FOR ETHICAL ISSUES	CODES
Issues related to use of Data and Technology	<p>Breach of data privacy and confidentiality -informational, volumetric and physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constant data capture without consent Data can be decoded and identified <p>Obfuscation of data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compromised informed consent <p>Misuse of data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surveillance, deception, indoctrination <hr/> <p>Navigating real and virtual lives</p> <p><i>Embodiment and re-entry problems</i> <i>Manipulation or interaction with avatars</i> <i>Individuals' awareness of Metaverse</i> <i>Avatars with self-awareness</i> <i>Development of tech without ethical reflection</i> <i>Dualism or unintended use of technology</i> <i>Attention distraction</i></p> <p>Trust</p> <p><i>Controlled social interactions</i> <i>Nudges</i></p>
Issues related to Human Rights- Societal & Individual	<p>Respect for persons and dignity -Society</p> <p>Discrimination - inclusivity and diversity - disabilities, marginalised populations, elderly</p> <p>Inequity and limited or no access</p> <p>Lack of representativeness in XR</p> <p><i>Sense of belonging</i></p> <p>Impact on vulnerable groups</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mental incapacitated Disabilities Children and youth Elderly <hr/> <p>Respect for persons and dignity -Individual</p> <p>HARM – Physical or Psychological and emotional harm</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safety, harassment, exploitation Addiction, hyper reality-mental health consequences due to AR content, virtual violence <p>OWNERSHIP AND INDIVIDUATION, IDENTITY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ownership of second lives ownership in the metaverse-avatars Virtual identity and concept of personal space <p>LOSS OF AGENCY</p> <p>Deception, therapeutic misconception Virtual identity Autonomy and consent</p>
Issues related to Society, Economy and Environment	<p>Negative impact on society</p> <p>- Social inclusivity- user acceptance</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainability & future generations - Criminal and anti-social behaviours - Cybercrimes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fraud • Identity theft • Harassment- Sexual • Hacking Impact on Economy - Monetisation Lack of or insufficient governance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jurisdiction • Ownership and property issues
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Table 4.0 Summary of Ethical issues.

3.2 Foundational Values and corresponding principles

Thematic analysis yielded six distinct theme categories for Values and approximately 22 principles. The process of connecting principles to relevant values was iterative. Eventually, there was consensus on the main values and related principles as represented in Table 5.0 below. The values are: 1) Respect for persons, 2) Well-being, 3) Safety, 4) Integrity and Trust, 5) Justice, 6) Responsiveness.

VALUES	PRINCIPLES
RESPECT FOR PERSONS	Freedom Informed consent Inclusion Right or ability to withdraw or stop Privacy and confidentiality Tolerance
WELL-BEING	Beneficence, positive psychological effects Prosperity
SAFETY	Non-maleficence Equivalence Risk and harm minimisation
INTEGRITY & TRUST	Accountability Fidelity Honesty Responsibility Sincere identity Transparency
JUSTICE	Accessibility, Equity, Reciprocity
RESPONSIVENESS	Anticipation Adaptivity

Table 5.0 Summary of foundational Values and Principles in immersive technologies

The most prominent values featured in more than 70% of the reviewed documents are respect, safety, and trust. Well-being and integrity featured in more than 50%. Responsiveness was the least featured value.

3.2.1 Respect for persons, Human Well-being, and Safety

Respect for persons is considered a fundamental human right, while human well-being should be the centre of the development and use of immersive technologies (Aymerich-Franch & Fosch-Villaronga, 2020; Behr et al., 2005; Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Magina, 2021; Southgate et al., 2017).

Safety was discussed in the context of avoiding or minimising harm and risks in developing and using immersive technologies (Aymerich-Franch & Fosch-Villaronga, 2020; Behr et al., 2005; Christopoulos et al., 2021; Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Luro et al., 2017). A safe virtual environment is fundamental to trust and a positive user experience (Behr et al., 2005; Bliznyuk, 2019; Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Ramirez et al., 2021; Smits et al., 2022). The principles connected to safety include non-maleficence and equivalence

(Bliznyuk, 2019; Ramirez et al., 2021, 2021). Safety warnings featured as a recommendation for users of headsets especially for the more vulnerable users such as children (Luro et al., 2017; Magina, 2021; Ramirez et al., 2021).

3.2.2 Integrity and Trust

Integrity and trust were noted as important values for consumers/users of technologies. Integrity of these technologies was interpreted as ensuring that regulatory frameworks and industrial standards were in place to facilitate public trust. One author notes the following:

Trust matters. It allows us to reveal vulnerable parts of ourselves to others, and to allow us to know others intimately in return. Moreover, on the societal level trust enhances our social capital. Thus, because augmented reality often supports interactions among persons –particularly interactions that have the potential to leave some persons vulnerable to the actions of other persons – it becomes crucial to design augmented reality such that trust can thrive (Friedman & Kahn, 2000).

Integrity was discussed both in terms of scientific processes and persons. Scientific integrity refers to designing systems that do not deceive or manipulate users. One author note:

XR designers sometimes incorporate strategies that deceive the user, hide the true intent of an interface element, or ultimately guide a person to do what they do not necessarily wish to do, or actions that may not be in their best interest. For instance, “dark”-carefully designed techniques such as bait and switch, hidden cost or misdirection-have been criticised as unethical to users (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021).

Individual integrity is important in relation to use of sincere identities (Eriksson, 2021; Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022).

3.2.3 Justice and Responsiveness

Justice was discussed to a great extent within the context of fairness, equality, and freedom from biases (Behr et al., 2005; Bliznyuk, 2019; Friedman & Kahn, 2000; Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Slater et al., 2020; Southgate et al., 2017; Stephens, 2022). One author notes that the development of technologies should be such that it “avoid(s) a situation where only privileged members of society benefit from technological advances” (Madary & Metzinger, 2016). The principles aligned to the attainment of justice are accessibility, equity, and reciprocity. To this end, researchers, developers and designers are implored to ensure that their systems should anticipate and mitigate against biases (Boyd-Noronha, 2020).

VALUES	NUMBER OF PAPERS
RESPECT	22
SAFETY	20
TRUST	17
WELL-BEING	16
JUSTICE	14
INTEGRITY	12
RESPONSIVENESS	3

Figure 5.0 Distribution of Values

3.2.4 Corresponding Principles

The dominant principles are privacy, informed consent, responsibility, transparency, and freedom which featured in approximately 50% of the reviewed documents. Privacy, freedom, and informed consent are foundational in respect for persons or users of immersive technologies. Transparency and responsibility refer to the integrity of the technologies and the developers.

Privacy, Confidentiality, Consent and Freedom

Privacy and informed consent to the use of personal data are the most fundamental principles in the development of XR technologies (Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Friedman & Kahn, 2000; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Pearlman, 2020; Ramirez et al., 2021, 2021; Southgate et al., 2017). The right to privacy and by extension non-interference is considered a Human right (Aymerich-Franch & Fosch-Villaronga, 2020). Confidentiality is a term closely aligned to protection of privacy (Boyd-Noronha, 2020).

The right to privacy is the right to one's identity in any form (including name, image, voice, preferences) remaining private, that is, not becoming publicly disclosed..... it is crucial to maintain the right to privacy of individuals given that disclosure of private information may be seriously harmful to the psychological well-being and social standing of the affected person (Slater et al., 2020, p. 6).

Freedom in the documents referred to non-manipulation and freedom of choice ((Aymerich-Franch & Fosch-Villaronga, 2020; Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016)

(Boyd-Noronha, 2020; Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Ramirez et al., 2021). It was closely associated with references to respect for autonomy and dignity (Behr et al., 2005; Boyd-Noronha, 2020; Fox & Thornton, 2022; Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Smits et al., 2022). According to IEEE, "agency is the capacity of individuals to act independently and to exercise free choice, a quality fundamental to democratic ideals" (IEEE: Ethically aligned Design). Loss of a sense of agency through manipulation and use of algorithms that foster dependence is considered an infringement of freedom and autonomy (Behr et al., 2005; Laurynas Adomaitis & Grinbaum, 2023; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Smits et al., 2022).

Business models that foster dependency and aim to maximise user attention for profit are unethical, as numerous studies have shown correlations with decreased quality of life, depression, anxiety, and other impacts on mental, physical, or social health... In contrast, XR designs could reject such algorithms and instead consider how to provide greater freedom and autonomy, self-regulation.....and connection with others (Lee & Hu-Au, 2021, p. 4).

Fidelity, Responsibility and Transparency

These are noted as integral principles to maintain trust in immersive technologies. Developers and users are expected to be responsible in development and conduct.

Agents who bear responsibility for virtual actions include the developer, the "trainer" (overseeing the selection of training data), the manufacturer, and the user. In each case, the sharing of responsibility should be determined depending on context (Laurynas Adomaitis & Grinbaum, 2023, p. 3)

Non-maleficence (Avoiding harm), Equivalence and the Right to withdraw/stop

Although not numerically significant in terms of the use of the explicit term "non-maleficence" in the reviewed documents, indirect reference was made to the synonymous term "avoiding or preventing harm" (Behr et al., 2005; Boyd-Noronha, 2020; Laurynas Adomaitis & Grinbaum, 2023; Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Smits et al., 2022). As discussed earlier, harm may be physical, psychological, or emotional. To this end, all principles are considered of significant relevance despite frequency of occurrence in texts. Two authors addressed non-maleficence using the equivalence principle (Bliznyuk, 2019; Ramirez et al., 2021). This principle is presented as rule of thumb for comparing harms in the physical and the virtual worlds.

The Equivalence principle states:

If it would be wrong to allow a person to have an experience of something in the real world, then it would be wrong to allow a person to a virtually real analogue of that experience. As a simulation's likelihood of inducing virtually real experiences in its subject increases, so too should the justification for the use of the simulation (Ramirez et al., 2021, p. 8).

The right to withdraw or stop participation in a VR experience is stressed as particularly important for users. In the context of research using VR, one author notes that:

Participants should be instructed how to quit the VR experience and to deposit the equipment in case of too intense emotions or the feeling of being stressfully overwhelmed by the virtual environment. During the procedure, an experimenter should be available in the laboratory who can assist the participants to terminate exposure and re-enter reality if severe discomfort, information overload, or anxiety arise (Behr et al., 2005, p. 672).

Inclusion, Accessibility, Tolerance and Equity

Inclusion and accessibility are principles aligned with the right to non-discrimination. These principles are noted as relevant to protecting fundamental human rights of respect for persons and dignity. The IEEE and the Cyber XR coalition emphasise the importance of "leaving no one behind" in the development of immersive technologies. Emphasis is placed on inclusion and access for persons with disabilities and tolerance for persons varying representations (physical, cultural, and otherwise) in the virtual space. One author highlights an already existing digital divide in society.

Certain groups of people already face the digital divide: women, the poor, the elderly, and the disabled. Not only does this gap need to be closed, but continuous Education will also be needed as new technologies are deployed and new economies developed (Stephens, 2022, p. 19).

Figure 6.0 Distribution of Principles

3.3 Normative Approaches to Addressing Ethical Issues

Themes that emerged as important approaches to resolving or addressing the various ethical issues with immersive technologies are organised into four domains: 1) Society/Governance, 2) Industry, 3) Research/Academic Organisations, and 4) Individuals. The term “Domain” is preferred as the approaches are not reported based on hierarchy or levels of importance. Nevertheless, we acknowledge that the broader governance issues are fundamental to success in other domains.

APPROACHES TO ADDRESS ETHICAL ISSUES WITH THE USE OF IMMERSIVE TECHNOLOGIES

Figure 7.0 Normative Approaches to addressing Ethical Issues of Immersive Technologies

3.3.1 Society/Governance

Within the societal domain, the ethical issues that would be addressed are related to data and technology and human rights. Many authors referenced data protection and civil/human rights laws and conventions. Recommendations are made for applying existing laws to immersive technologies and the subsequent enforcement of these laws. These recommendations note the need to protect privacy, prevent data misuse, ensure consumer rights, protect children, and prevent discrimination (Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Ramirez et al., 2021; Southgate et al., 2017).

Another important step would be the official recognition of virtual identity. Recommendation was made in the context of applying copyright laws to virtual identities, particularly virtual clones (Eriksson, 2021; Stephens, 2022). Other areas to be addressed would be ownership of virtual space concerning property and avatars (Eriksson, 2021; Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Stephens, 2022). Guidelines are recommended for addressing economic disparities and the possibility of exploitation. Concerns related to virtual crimes could be addressed by examining what should be considered a crime in the virtual space and applying relevant cybercrime laws. Jurisdiction would need to be clarified (Slater et al., 2020; Stephens, 2022).

3.3.2 Industry

In addressing the ethical issues related to the use of technology, the authors stressed the importance of an inclusive design, development and implementation approach (Boyd-Noronha, 2020; Davis et al., 2021; Fox & Thornton, 2022; Friedman & Kahn, 2000; Southgate et al., 2017). Although there are variations in the approaches presented, the most common theme was that technology development should be "human-centred, safe, and value-sensitive" (Boyd-Noronha, 2020; Davis et al., 2021; Fox & Thornton, 2022; Friedman & Kahn, 2000). Suggestions were made for adopting existing codes of ethics or standards and tailoring these to the particular technologies in use. To this end, several authors presented their recommendations in the forms of self-identified codes of conduct, guidelines, tools, and considerations to developers, researchers, educators, and industry practitioners (Aymerich-Franch &

Fosch-Villaronga, 2020; Bliznyuk, 2019; Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022; Smits et al., 2022). The need for a standardised methodology across the industry was noted (Magina, 2021). Another relevant recommendation was an interdisciplinary collaboration (Davis et al., 2021; Eriksson, 2021). Several examples of these laws and codes are listed in Table 6.0 below.

3.3.3 Research and Academic Organisations

Researchers featured as one of the main target audiences, especially concerning health and education (Aymerich-Franch & Fosch-Villaronga, 2020; Bliznyuk, 2019; Lee & Hu-Au, 2021; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Smits et al., 2022; Southgate et al., 2017). The use of technology in these fields may cause unintended long-term effects. Several authors recommended that researchers should be guided by the existing normative documents for ethics in research, such as the Belmont Report, the Nuremberg Code and the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki. Reference was made to the Convention on the Rights of the Child for the protection of children (Davis et al., 2021; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Slater et al., 2020; Southgate et al., 2017). Examples of immersive technologies in health were in relation to VR experiences, especially for the improvement of psychological well-being. Reference was made to the American and British Psychological Associations' Codes of Conduct along with relevant research ethics guidelines (Behr et al., 2005; Bliznyuk, 2019; Madary & Metzinger, 2016). Several authors presented unique perspectives and self-identified codes with reference to fundamental normative theories such as computer or technology ethics and deontological or teleological approaches to addressing ethical challenges (Behr et al., 2005; Friedman & Kahn, 2000; Smits et al., 2022). It was observed, however, that variations may need careful examination for comprehension and completeness in addressing all identified ethical issues. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) or Research ethics committee was acknowledged as having a role to play in assessing the possible harms of using VR in research (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Southgate et al., 2017). However, it was not noted whether the IRB has the knowledge or capacity to conduct this type of assessment (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Southgate et al., 2017). Clinical oversight or clinicians' involvement in research is another recommendation (Madary & Metzinger, 2016).

3.3.4 Individuals

User involvement and empowerment were noted as integral to the success of ethically aligned designs (Behr et al., 2005; Fox & Thornton, 2022; The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, 2019). Increasing user awareness of the negative effects of immersive experiences and enabling users to exit VR experiences were noted as important to user empowerment (Cortese & Outlaw, 2021; The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, 2019). Avoidance of data obfuscation and information overload to ensure valid informed consent regarding different types of immersive experiences before users enter a virtual space was emphasised (Behr et al., 2005; Fox & Thornton, 2022; Luro et al., 2017; Madary & Metzinger, 2016). The use of sincere identities and not engaging in anti-social or criminal behaviours was also noted as a personal responsibility of users (Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022).

DOMAINS	ETHICAL ISSUES	RECOMMENDED APPROACHES	EXAMPLES GIVEN	EXCERPTS FROM DOCUMENTS
SOCIETY - GOVERNANCE	<i>Ethical issues related to use of Data and technology and, human rights</i>	Application and enforcement of existing laws to XR technologies <i>Data protection and privacy laws</i>	GDPR, HIPAA, California Consumer Privacy Act, Children online privacy protection Act (COPPA) Family Education rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) Title VI of the Civil Rights Act of Higher Education	AR applications raise concerns about reasonable expectations of privacy in public space, as they cannot only record audio-visual information, but also process and aggregate data about a user's surroundings in real time. This information gathering may present special considerations for bystander privacy, especially when

<p><i>Constitutional</i></p> <p><i>Consumer rights</i></p> <p><i>Protection of children</i></p> <p><i>Anti-discrimination</i></p> <p><i>Accessibility laws</i></p>	<p>European Accessibility Act</p> <p>The US Rehabilitation Act</p> <p>The American Disabilities Act</p> <p>Convention on the Rights of the Child</p>	<p>government and law enforcement use the technology. To address potential concerns, the Department of Justice should issue guidelines for law enforcement development and implementation of AR/VR solutions to ensure they maintain First and Fourth Amendment rights protections for the communities in which they deploy this technology (Fox & Thornton, 2022)</p>
<p>Governance Guidelines</p>	<p>South Korean Government ethics guidelines for the Metaverse</p>	<p>Developers or operators should be aware that the development and operation methods established today may affect the future Metaverse and thus not misuse the Metaverse. They should try to ensure that the Metaverse becomes sustainable (Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022)</p>
<p>Official recognition of virtual identity</p>	<p>Copyright, identity card and body right</p>	<p>The capability for (original) individuals to claim the right to their identity and achieve control over the use of their virtual clones needs to be strengthened. It is beneficial to formulate this right in a familiar way. This will make it easier to explain and discuss. Therefore, it is suggested that a person right law is formulated based on copyright. Such a law could mimic the two-part structure of copyright, so that there is an "economic right" controlling who can use the identity and a "moral right" controlling the original individuals' right to be connected to the virtual clone. Until such a law is internationally put in place, developers of mixed reality experiences should use the concept as a guiding principle. Note that an alternative term would be bodyright (Eriksson, 2021).</p>

	<p>Ownership of avatars and virtual space</p>	<p>Avatar ownership will be an important issue for regulatory agencies to consider. There are strong reasons to place restrictions on the way in which avatars can be used, such as protecting the interests and privacy of individuals who strongly identify with their own particular avatar on social networks. On the other hand, these restrictions may prove impractical to implement and may unnecessarily limit personal creative freedom. Regulators must strike a rational balance between these concern(Eriksson, 2021; Stephens, 2022)</p>
	<p>Measures to address Virtual crimes and jurisdiction</p>	<p>Jurisdiction</p> <p>Regarding regulatory challenges, jurisdiction becomes more critical. For example, whose national jurisdiction does a virtual-world crime fall under? (Stephens, 2022)</p>
<p>INDUSTRY -BEST PRACTICE</p>	<p><i>Ethical issues related to use of technology</i></p> <p>Inclusive Design, development, and implementation</p>	<p>An Ethical Code for Commercial VR/AR applications- Equivalence principle</p> <p>Safety by Design Human rights framework XRSI Privacy framework</p> <p>Self-assessment using RRI framework</p> <p>Value sensitive design</p> <p>Code of ethics- Assc. for Computing machinery</p> <p>ISO 26000:2010 on Social Responsibility</p> <p>Software Engineering Code of Ethics</p> <p>If it would be wrong to allow a person to have an experience of something in the real world, then it would be wrong to allow a person to a virtually real analogue of that experience. As a simulation's likelihood of inducing virtually-real experiences in its subject increases, so too should the justification for the use of the simulation (Ramirez et al., 2021)</p> <p>RRI promotes reflection upon the consequences of the outcomes of technology and fosters the incorporation of such reflections into the research and design processes. The five principles of inclusion, anticipation, reflection, responsiveness, and transparency that define RRI provide a suitable framework for conducting research and innovating responsibly in any</p>

	<p>Standardised methodology Inter-disciplinary collaboration Warnings</p>	<p>area of R&I, including embodiment technologies (Aymerich-Franch & Fosch-Villaronga, 2020)</p> <hr/> <p>Safety by Design is all about enabling trust in systems, designs, and data so that organisations can lead to transformational change and innovate with confidence. The need for such an approach is becoming more evident every day (Boyd-Noronha, 2020)</p> <hr/> <p>Working together to develop software allows all parties to bring their expertise to the Design; and the collaborative dialogue often leads to the identification of issues that neither party would independently observe, resulting in an overall improvement of the work's quality</p> <hr/> <p>Value-Sensitive Design is primarily concerned with values that center on human well-being, human dignity, Justice, welfare, and human rights (Friedman & Kahn, 2000).</p>	
<p>RESEARCH & Academic ORGANISATIONS</p>	<p>Ethical issues related to individuals in Education and research</p>	<p>Prior ethics review and longitudinal studies to measure effects</p> <p>IRB Protocol review and approval</p>	<p>if there is a possibility of affecting physically or psychologically a research participant, an IRB would require from a researcher to have a protocol in place if the participant experiences discomfort during or after the study (Madary & Metzinger, 2016)</p> <hr/> <p>Longitudinal studies and further research into the psychological effects of long-term immersion are needed (Madary & Metzinger, 2016)</p>

	<p>Development of new and application of existing Codes of ethics for Educators and Researchers</p>	<p>Existing</p> <p>Belmont report, Nuremburg Code the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki, the Belmont Report, APA Code of Ethics,</p> <p>Proposed:</p> <p>ARLEAN</p> <p>Real Virtuality: A Code of Ethical conduct</p> <p>E3XR: An Analytical Framework for ethical educational and Eudaimonic Design</p> <p>Guidance Ethics</p>	<p>The development of contemporary ethical principles in human research can be traced to the Nuremburg Code, the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki, the Belmont Report and human rights frameworks such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child (Southgate et al., 2017)</p> <hr/> <p>The approach to guidance ethics in the context we proposed here, is even more suitable for merging Design with assessment. In healthcare, it is commonly challenging to involve the right users in the design process and embedding technology design within current healthcare services and protocols. A practice-based guidance ethics approach can support designers to optimally embed user needs and values in technology design (Smits et al., 2022)</p>	
	<p>Clinical oversight</p>	<p>Real Virtuality: A Code of Ethical conduct</p>	<p>VR researchers aiming at new clinical applications should work in close collaboration with physicians who may be better situated to make informed judgments about the suitability of particular patients for new trials (Madary & Metzinger, 2016).</p>	
<p>INDIVIDUALS</p>	<p>Ethical issues related to individuals on a personal level</p>	<p>User empowerment</p>	<p>Warnings, informed consent, able to enter and exit VR</p>	<p>Upon entering any virtual realm, individuals should be provided information about the nature of algorithmic tracking and mediation within any environment. This will allow not only for consent regarding the use of their personal data, but for improved trust between individuals and creators of these environments regarding user experience. This could also include a "serendipity on or off" button allowing a user to express their desire for</p>

		randomness as well (The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, 2019)
Identity	Sincere identity	it is proposed that members of society aim for 'sincere identity, safe experience, and sustainable prosperity' in the process of participating in the metaverse ecosystem to maximise its potential. In the Metaverse, individuals should be faithful to the values (Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022)

Table 6.0 Normative Approaches in four domains

4 Summary and Discussion

The goal of this scoping review is to identify ethical issues in relation to the use of immersive technologies and the related foundational principles and approaches to addressing these issues. The overarching research question guiding this review process is: What are the relevant ethical frameworks, codes of conduct and good practices related to XR? We chose the scoping review methodology because it enables knowledge synthesis from a wide cross-section of literature over time. To this end, we identified 28 documents that self-identified as ethical frameworks, codes, or good practices related to XR from grey and academic literature using a pre-determined search and eligibility criteria. The literature search includes documents between 2000 and 2023 written in English. Thematic analysis generated four categories of ethical issues, six values with 22 accompanying principles and four domains addressed in the various approaches.

We note that issuers from the USA and Europe wrote most of the included documents. However, the issuers were representative of academia, industry, government, and professional and non-profit organisations. South Korea is the only identified government organisation that issued ethical guidelines for the Metaverse. It may be relevant to note the non or under-representation of issuers from Asia, Africa, and South and Central America. This may either be a limitation of the eligibility criteria to the English language only or an indication of where ethical guidance on immersive technologies are predominantly coming from.

Nevertheless, it may be relevant to note that the 2021 scoping review of AI Ethics guidelines that did not have a similar language restriction also reflected the under-representation of these geographic regions. Although the USA and Europe were noted as the leading issuers of the reviewed documents, we did not identify a similar ethics guideline as that issued by the South Korean Government for the Metaverse or the use of specific immersive technologies. However, a non-profit organization, Cyber XR Coalition, made recommendations to the Biden administration. The IEEE, a global organization for technology practitioners, issued several recommendations addressing different areas of ethical challenges with immersive technologies to governments, research, and academic and private organizations. Most of these recommendations were published between 2021 and 2022.

4.1 Dominance of principles-based ethics

The different guidance documents have varying lists of principles and values/virtues, with some of the principles and values/virtues more common than others and it remains to be seen if a consensus is to be reached among the various stakeholders from the various global regions. The values and principles that are less emphasised may also be an indication of areas that need more work. We will be able to see which ethical issues emerge in terms of magnitude and frequency, which may confirm or deny the latter claim.

Aside from the above-mentioned observation, it was also noticeable that all the reviewed documents adapt a principles-based approach to ethical justification. By principles-based approach, we refer to a specific way of doing ethics characterized by the identification of guiding principles/values/virtues, none which hold primacy over the other (Beauchamp & Childress, 2019). This approach was championed by biomedical ethicists, Tom Beauchamp and James Childress, who presented four arguably universal and co-equal principles that are balanced off against each other in the settling of an ethical question or dilemma (Beauchamp & Childress, 2019). The approach has been criticized for arbitrariness of its procedure for moral justification and the legitimacy of the list of principles, and the same criticism may be lodged to the different guidance documents considering that they all have the same ethical foundation (Duwell, 2014). This finding may be translated into learnings that must be taken into consideration by WP5 in the drafting of the guidance document, including the following:

- a. That principlism is an intuitively acceptable approach utilized in guidance documents, which may be an indication of a convenient approach for the XR4Human's guidance document.
- b. Considering the limitations of the approach as reflected in the literature, XR4Human's guidance may wish to address this by including other approaches to doing ethics that, based on the succeeding deliverables of WP2, prove to be useful not only in the elaboration of the ethical issue at hand but also sufficiently guiding for the intended stakeholders.

4.2 Some Gaps in the literature

The reviewed papers that discussed ethical issues and normative approaches in relation to the use of immersive technologies in health were mainly centred on ethical issues concerning the field of psychology. The welfare of children using immersive technologies was widely discussed, with children identified as the most vulnerable group. Southgate et al. discussed in-depth some of the possible negative consequences of research on children and youth using immersive technology. The authors emphasized an ethics-in-practice approach, i.e., continued vigilance in research with children (Southgate et al., 2017). Other authors discussed the possibility of various forms of developmental harm as well as infringement on the privacy of children (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Pearlman, 2020; Southgate et al., 2017). It was noted that children are particularly vulnerable because their brains are not "fully developed" (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Southgate et al., 2017). There appears to be a gap in terms of unknown long-term consequences on the development of children (physical, psychological, and cognitive). There is limited information related to the eye safety of children. However, the technology, through its simulation of 3D, breaks down a neurological link that operates in natural/physical environments that is essential for eyes and visual function to develop normally (normal development is also preventive of eye disease in later life) (Pladere et al., 2022). Consequently, if eyes and vision do not develop normally persons could be excluded from using this technology (Pladere et al., 2022). Although some authors discussed some industry best practices, such as warnings against the use of head mount devices by children under 13 years, the need for adult supervision, and limiting virtual time, it was not considered sufficient and possibly disingenuous (Southgate et al., 2017). Applying some existing normative frameworks, such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the US Children's Online Privacy Protection Rule (COPPA), were considered relevant to guiding developers (Pearlman, 2020; Southgate et al., 2017).

The use of immersive technologies within the workplace is mentioned in the context of inclusion in one document (Fox & Thornton, 2022). This is identified as a gap in that there has been increased use of immersive technologies in workspaces, and attention needs to be placed on the impact (positive or

negative) on these spaces. If the technology is not inclusive of all then this raises ethical concerns. Current commercially available XR tech may only be comfortable to wear for about 50–60% of the population (Pladere et al., 2022), which is similar to that found in Deliverable 6.1 where current XR technology was reported to be accessible to only about half of the population. If a worker needs to use this technology to fulfil daily tasks/obligations, but it does not fit and is not comfortable to wear or use for any length of time, and one cannot wear the prescription correction you need while using the technology – it will put the worker at a disadvantage. It may be noted as a disability.

Although several texts note a role for Ethics Committees, no information was shared on the competence or capacity of Ethics Committees to evaluate immersive technologies. Discussions were limited to the need for a review of research for potential harm to participants and follow-up of research involving children/youth (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Southgate et al., 2017).

5 Limitations and Conclusions

Although the Librarian's expertise is essential in conducting a comprehensive search, the choice of databases also has its limits. Using a scoping review, descriptive statistics combined with a qualitative analysis method has inherent limitations. One limitation is the possible exclusion of relevant texts based on predefined search terms. Additionally, we also limited the search to texts in English. There is also the challenge of not identifying essential policy documents that may not be indexed to facilitate retrieval using our search procedures. Thematic analysis is also subject to bias, although we attempted to minimize this by using several coders, an inductive coding strategy, and regular meetings.

Ethical issues related to misuse of data, breach of privacy, misuse of technologies, human rights concerns, and wider societal challenges such as exploitation, sustainability, and crimes. Several authors presented approaches which we have coded within four main domains: Society, Industry, Research/Academic Organizations, and Individuals. Although there are variations in approaches across the documents, the central themes to addressing ethical issues in immersive technologies are hinged on the fundamental values of respect for persons, human well-being, safety, trust and integrity, justice and responsiveness and their accompanying principles. We note that proper governance frameworks, inclusive human-centric technology development, and user empowerment are essential to successfully addressing ethical challenges. Several existing normative approaches were presented in the literature, and new suggestions to address unique challenges. Nevertheless, we note gaps that may need to be further explored. The South Korean Government appears to have taken the lead in tendering ethics guidelines at a governmental level (Ministry of Science and ICT, 2022). There is a disparity in the geographic distribution of issuers, indicating a possible underrepresentation in the literature. We also note that health was discussed mainly in the context of psychology. The protection of vulnerable groups, especially children, was noted. However, there is concern that enough is still not known regarding the intermediate and long-term effects of immersive technologies.

Note that while XR is already being applied in many bubbles, it is not a technology that is available to the masses. Consequently, research in this area is generally fragmentary or lags behind the increasingly rapid pace of technical development. This is another reason why there are comparatively few studies dealing with ethical principles and why it is so important to develop ethical guidelines and to establish them legally.

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